

THE ROLE OF MOTHERS FOR FAMILY WELFARE IN PREVENTING THE RISE OF VIOLENCE IN THE HOUSEHOLDS IN NORTH SAMARINDA SUB-DISTRICT EAST KALIMANTAN

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Abstract , *The purpose of the Community Partnership Program is to increase the participation of mothers of family welfare counselors in preventing violence in women and children. The method used is Normative Research Type, with Qualitati Descriptive type. The approach taken is the approach of legislation and conceptual approach. Respondents are mothers of Family Welfare Coaches in North Samarinda District. Technique of collecting data by doing observation first then then do interview and by collecting documentation.*

The role of Development of the family welfare mothers is always expected in the development of the nation, since women and children are the end of tomak progress of a country. Because if women and children are sick then all the elements that there will be a pain. Likewise a country can advance because of its youth, so it is likened that 1000 parents can only dream but one young man can change the world.

But in reality it is inversely proportional to women and children have always been victims of male crime. But in reality it is inversely proportional to women and children have always been victims of male crime. Along in carrying out its main tasks are ten Development of family welfare programs.

Keywords: *Anak, Peran ibu PKK , Kekerasan, Pencegahan, Perempuan*

1) INTRODUCTION

The basis for assessing violence against women and children is Law no. Law No. 23 of 2004 on the Elimination of Domestic Violence; Law No. 35 of 2014 on child protection. Violent crime as a phenomenon in society has developed both in terms of motive, nature, form, frequency, intensity, and modus operandi especially after the multidimensional crisis hit Indonesia. Characteristics of increasing the quality of violence can be expressed, among others, in terms of modus operadi all only used sharp weapons, transportation equipment and communication tools. Now the

perpetrators have used firearms, radio equipment and chemicals to commit crimes. Similarly, the increase in the original motive of crime is done to meet basic daily needs, then develop along with other motives such as killing for the purpose of earning a lot of money. In terms of the target aspect of the original victims of crime are the adults and then developing women and children. The enactment of Law No. 23/2004 was not free from the above developments. This Act regulates the protection of women in a more comprehensive manner to protect and side with women victim, and at the same time provide education and

awareness to the community and apparatus that all acts of domestic violence are a crime against human dignity.

In the Legal Territory of Samarinda Polytechnic, in 2011-2014, some notes from the database of cases of Domestic Violence as follows:

- of 10 wives have experienced violence committed by husbands and ex-husbands (83.1%).
- 4 attempts were made by women who experienced violence, by asking for family assistance (32.26%), legal services (24.37%), health services (16.48%) or silent (13.26%) .
- Almost 6% of women are children who experience sexual violence and neglect.
- 9 out of 10 women experience more than one form of violence (beganda and layered). Only 7.17% of those subjected to single violent domestic violence, whether physical, psychological, sexual and domestic outbreaks and disputes
- 9 out of 10 women suffered the impact of violence affecting the mental health of the victims (97.84%) including suicide

attempts. While 1 in 10 wives experienced reproductive health effects. The purpose of this devotion is to strengthen the role of the unity of mothers of Family Welfare Development in the prevention of Violence against Women and Children in North Samarinda.

2) RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used is normative legal research. With an analytic descriptive type aimed at explaining the role of PKK mothers in preventing the rampant acts of violence of women and children in North Samarinda district¹.

In describing the variables in this study contained therein indicators as part of a scientific search effort that will be described and analyzed indicator by using the approach as follows:

he philosophy approach is to know the role of women in the development of family welfare in the prevention of violence against women and children.

The conceptual approach is (conceptual approach), that is by moving on the views and doctrines that developed in law science so that a new idea can be found and the principles relevant to the problem being studied. Approach in the Law

¹ Menurut Peter Marzuki, penelitian hukum normatif cukup disebut penelitian hukum, karena istilah *legal research* atau dalam bahasa Belanda disebut *rechtsonderzoek* selalu normatif. Demikian pula istilah yuridis-normatif juga dikenal dalam penelitian hukum,

sehingga istilah yang tepat adalah menggunakan penelitian hukum. Sebagaimana tertuang dalam Peter Marzuki, 2009., Penelitian Hukum Edisi revisi, Jakarta. Hal. 55-56.

(Statute approach) and Concept Approach (Concept approach).

The legal substances used in this study consist of; primary, secondary and tertiary legal materials². Primary legal materials in the form of legislation related to Violence against women and children and its implementing regulations. Secondary legal materials in the form of legal literature related to the management of coal mining, legal materials obtained from the internet, seminar results, research results, symposia and results of workshops related to the object of research. While tertiary legal material that is supporting documents, such as statistical data and monographs and other similar.

3) RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Prevention of evil is much better than trying to educate the villain to be good again, but this does not mean that the perpetrator of a crime will never return. In connection with this according to Abdulsyani conception of criminal penanggugangan are³: in general, efforts to overcome crime is done by moralistic method, which means coaching is done by shaping the spiritual mental towards the positive, for example can be done by educators, religious experts,

psychologists and so forth. Unless it can also be used abolitionistic method, that is guidance performed in a conceptual manner which must be planned on the basis of the results of criminological research, planned on the basis of criminological research results, planned on the basis of criminological research results, by exploring the sources of causes of factors related to crime.

This method of mitigation conceptually will be more effective if accompanied by the operational method of prevention is done by the police.

Crime prevention by the police includes preventive and repressive action against crime. Enterprises that demonstrate educational guidance, and awareness of the general public prior to the onset of crime, are essentially preventive or preventive measures.

While efforts that show efforts to eradicate criminal acts that are happening is a repressive action. Repressive efforts at once can be a preventive measure, because by committing acts to perpetrators of crime, potential perpetrators or persons will commit a crime or feel afraid to do.

The protection of the law shall be to protect the right of everyone to equal

² Roni Hanitjo Soemitro, Metodologi Penelitian Hukum dan Jurimetri, (Penerbit Ghalia Indonesia Jakarta, 1998). Hal. 125

³Abdulsyani., *Kejahatan dan penyimpangan Suatu Perspektif Kriminologi.*, Bina Aksara., Jakarta. 1987., Hal.27

treatment and protection to the law and the law, hence for any violation of the law alleged to a person and the consequences he sought. He shall have the right to obtain the necessary legal protection in accordance with the principle of a lawful State.⁴ According to

Satjipto Raharjo legal protection is to provide protection for human rights harmed by others and the protection is given to the community in order to enjoy all the rights granted by law.⁵

Cases of violence that rampant in Samarinda Utara is an affair that affects psychologically to the wife and children. The contributing factor is the depletion of belief and obedience to religion. According to the author if a man has a strong belief in religion then it is difficult to turn to the temptations of a world that is so challenging in life. Love of religion is certainly embodied in the love of the family. Even families become a priority scale. But what happens is generally a man of different minds, he seeks pleasure, pleases other women, then sacrifices those who love him. Which is not necessarily a woman affair loves her full of heart.⁶ Minimal religious understanding

⁴Mukadimah Konsep Penyempurnaan Anggaran Dasar, Peraturan Rumah Tangga, Kode Etik Advokat, Hukum Acara Dewan Kehormatan untuk disyahkan Konggres ke 6 peradilan di Bandung, Tanggal 4-6-1981, Panitia Penyelenggaraan Konggres peradilan.

⁵Satjipto Rahardjo, Penyelenggaraan

makes internal conflicts that occur in the staircase to trigger the occurrence of adultery.

Though the affair is not the way out if there is a problem in the household. Maintaining healthy, open and intense communication between partners is a solution to resolve internal problems in the household. If in the relationship of husband and wife is no longer a match with through several internal mediation efforts of the extended family but the husband survives with an affair and still do not want to split the only path is polygamy, although the wife's side a big and unpleasant calamity was born as well as inner.

But it may be something that is painful in human opinion but Allah wills the other. Of course with consideration for the sake of children. Because the fact in the field generally children do not want to be called not have a father or father owned by others⁷.

If there is no match after some problem-solving process then the husband can do polygamy, this if the wife and husband do

Keadilan dalam Masyarakat yang sedang Berubah, Jurnal Masalah-Masalah Hukum, No. 1-6, TahunX/10/2007

⁶ Kasus, temuan di lapangan september 2017

⁷ Temuan di lapangan September 2017.

not want divorce, and this is better than divorce.

But if both seek a divorce, although with any effort made to unite still choose to split up then do the divorce by forced. Due to the causes of destruction of the household, the loss of a husband and children can be depressed.

Thus it is necessary to understand that human beings as social beings can always give a humane contribution for the survival of a happy, healthy, safe and sentosa.

The second case was a father who had the heart to impregnate his child until he became pregnant.

Suspected cause is the state of a small house and a small even do not have a room so that when there is a chance the father abusive own child until pregnant. Dad's actions are repeatedly done when the wife goes out. Children can not refuse because they threatened to be killed by his father.

This case is caught when the child's age of seven months. And the child is finally open to express his pregnancy.⁸

Responding to cases above women as a whole need to have a high stock of science so that can perform a strong movement simultaneously so that women are not oppressed above the men. It is realized that human beings are social beings and therefore always share

goodness and not close themselves for a good.

Related to the rampant issue of violence in women and children, it is necessary to empower women's unity in the name of the mother group of Family Welfare Development to move in the development to prevent the rise of violence in women and children.

This role as part of the responsibility of Family Welfare Development in empowering women, so that not only knowledgeable, but trained to bsa gave birth to many positive works.

According to G. Peter Hoefnagels, the Crime Agreement could be divided into two, namely the first through the penal path (Penal Code) and through the non-penal path (not or outside the criminal law). In the division of G.P. Hoefnagels attempts mentioned in point (1) are penal efforts whereas for (2) and (3) are non-penal measures.

Efforts to overcome crimes through penal channels are more focused on the nature of repressive or suppression / eradication / crackdown after the crime occurred. While the non-penal path is more focused on the nature of preventive or prevention / deterrence / control before the crime occurs. It is said to be roughly different, since repressive action can essentially be seen as a preventive action in the broadest sense.⁹

⁸Kasus di lapangan September 2017

⁹Sudarto., Kapita Selektta Hukum

The author agrees with G.P. Hoefnagels that to address violent crimes through preventive or lane prevention called non-penal. Non-penal efforts in tackling crime are closely related to penal businesses. This non penalty effort by itself will greatly support the implementation of criminal justice in achieving its objectives. Prevention or tackling crime should be an integral approach between penal and non-penal means.

The primary objective of non-penalties is to address the conducive factors that cause crime. These conducive factors, among other things, center on social problems or conditions that can directly or indirectly generate or nourish crime.

Thus, judging from a macro-political and global perspective of criminal politics, non-penal efforts occupy key and strategic positions of overall criminal politics.

At the United Nations Congress on the Prevention of Crime and Treatment of Offenders emphasized strategic efforts to overcome the causes of crime.

Some of the problems and social conditions that can be a conducive factor for the cause of a crime are obviously problems that can not be solved solely with penal. This is where the limitation of the penal path and therefore must be supported by the non-penal path.

One of the "non penal" lanes to overcome social problems as mentioned above is through social policy.

Which in theory G.P. Hoefnagels above are also included in the path of prevention without punishment.

Social policy is basically a policy or a rational effort to achieve community welfare.

So it is synonymous with national development policy or planning which covers a wide range of aspects of development.

One aspect of social policy that would be worthy of attention is the cultivation of social hygiene issues, both individually as members of the community as well as the health / welfare of the family (including the welfare of children and youth), and the wider community in general. Cultivation of mental health problems, national mental health and child welfare is also expressed in the above Hoefnagels scheme as one path prevention (of crime) without punishment (non-penal path).

Prof. Sudarto has also pointed out that the activities of youth combatants, scout activities and the cultivation of mental health of the people with religious education are non-penal efforts in preventing and overcoming crime.

Some of the preventive measures described above are examples of non-penalties. However, the most strategic is

all efforts to make the community as a healthy social and environmental environment (materially and immaterial) of criminogenic factors. This means, the community with all its potential must be used as an antidote to the crime or anti criminogen factor that is an integral part of the overall criminal politics.

In addition to nonpenal efforts can be pursued by nourishing the community through social policies and by multiplying the potential within the community itself, it can also be extracted from other sources that also have the potential of preventive effects.

Other sources are, for example, the press / mass media, the utilization of technological advances (known as techno-prevention) and the utilization of the preventive-effect potency of law enforcement officers.

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To prevent violence against women and children should be carried out:

1. Guidance and supervision of the marriage process
2. Increased knowledge and skills

3. Optimization of 8 family functions and patterns of effective and dialogical communication
4. Increase awareness and social awareness
5. Building a community-based protection system
6. Optimizing the role of community activity centers (posyandu, karang taruna, majelis taklim)
7. Revitalization of material and moral values
8. Initiation of child-friendly school (SRA)
9. Optimization of cooperation with the school committee
10. Conduct the preparation, revision, and synchronization of policies
11. Coordinate with law enforcement officials to organize court proceedings with fair discourse.

Certainly to protect, prevent and overcome violence against women and children all components of society must commit themselves to:

- a) Protect women and children according to their dignity and dignity and prevent violence and discrimination.
- b) Advocate for the community in the prevention and handling of trafficking in persons of violence against women and children.
- c) Facilitate, provide counseling and assistance to victims of trafficking

in persons and violence against women and children.

- d) Coordinate and cooperate with all levels of society and authorities in preventing, recognizing, finding and tackling trafficking victims and violence against women and children

As Mothers of Family Welfare Builders should understand the modus operandi of violent crime that often affects women and children. As Mothers of Family Welfare Builders should understand the modus operandi of violent crime that often affects women and children. In order to provide understanding As the role of the mother of the Family Welfare Coach is the appreciation and practice of Pancasila; mutual cooperation; food; clothing, housing and household management; education and skills; health; development of cooperative life; preserving the environment; with sound planning.

4) CONCLUSION

The role of mothers Pembina Family Welfare is always expected in the development of human resources. Because women have always been victims of men.

empowerment of mothers of Family Welfare Coaches to be able to play a role in providing protection, advocating,

Sudarto., Kapita Selektta Hukum Pidana, 1981., Hal. 118

facilitating and coordinating. Besides having a role is also tasked to implement and socialize ten programs of Family Welfare Development, namely the appreciation and practice of Pancasila; mutual cooperation; food; clothing, housing and household management; education and skills; health; development of cooperative life; preserving the environment; with sound planning.

5). REFERENSI

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Peter Marzuki, 2009., Penelitian Hukum Edisi¹ Roni Hanitijo Soemitro, Metodologi Penelitian Hukum dan Jurimetri, (Penerbit Ghalia Indonesia Jakarta, 1998).